

Article

EFFECT OF FLASH CARDS DRILLS ON OMISSION OF WORD-ENDINGS AMONG SENIOR SECONDARY STUDENTS WITH POST-LINGUAL HEARING IMPAIRMENT IN SPECIAL EDUCATION CENTRE, BAUCHI

Ruth Asabe Magaji & Roseline Amos Aku

Editor-in-chief
Dr. Jummai Jerry

Editors

1. Prof. Abu Egwa Ozegya
2. Prof. Gladys Belinda Babudoh
3. Prof. Terfa Ahon Adaka
4. Dr. Rufus Olanrewaju Adebisi

Article

EFFECT OF FLASH CARDS DRILLS ON OMISSION OF WORD-ENDINGS AMONG SENIOR SECONDARY STUDENTS WITH POST-LINGUAL HEARING IMPAIRMENT IN SPECIAL EDUCATION CENTRE, BAUCHI

Ruth Asabe Magaji ^{1*} & Roseline Amos Aku ²

¹ Department of Special Needs Education and Rehabilitation Sciences,
University of Jos, Jos,
Plateau State, Nigeria

² Department of Educational Foundations,
University of Jos, Jos,
Plateau State, Nigeria

*Correspondence: ruthasabemagaji@gmail.com (RAM)

check for
updates

Citation: Magaji, R. A. & Aku, R. A. (2026). Effect of Flash Cards Drills on Omission of Word-Endings among Senior Secondary Students with Post-Lingual Hearing Impairment in Special Education Centre, Bauchi State. *Nas. State Uni. J. of Spe. & Inclusive Edu*; 1(1), 64–71. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19396544>

Academic Editor: Dr. Jummai Jerry

Received: 14 November, 2025

Revised: 8 December, 2025

Accepted: 3 February, 2026

Published: 1 April, 2026

Copyright: © 2026 by the authors. Published by Department of Special Education, Nasarawa State University, Keffi, In collaboration with Zhimmai Publishing House, Keffi, Nigeria. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Abstract: *Students with omission of word-endings resulting from post-lingual hearing impairment face increased risks of social, emotional and oral language challenges relative to their typical speech. The performance of these students is poor in oral language-related subjects. This study examined the effects of flash cards drill on omission of word-endings performance of students with post-lingual hearing impairment in Special Education Centre Bauchi. Two research questions and two hypotheses were tested. Single-subject experimental design was adopted where the participants served as both the control and treatment group. A sample of five students was purposively selected. Audiological Assessment and Word Recognition Tests were employed for data collection and analyzed using mean and percentage. Validity of the instrument was made by two experts- Research, Measurement and Evaluation unit and Special Education and Rehabilitation Science, University of Jos. t-test for dependent samples was utilized to test hypotheses. The results revealed that flash cards drilling had significant effects on omission of word-endings performance of students with post-lingual hearing impairment. The post-test result showed great reductions in the number of errors. Based on these, recommendations were proffered among which is the need for teachers and schools for students with post-lingual impairment to inculcate flash card drill in the school's time table as method of addressing omission of word-endings.*

Keywords: Omission of word-ending, flash cards drill, hearing impairment

Introduction

Hearing impairment constitutes a significant sensory disability characterized by a partial or total inability to perceive auditory stimuli, which consequently affects communication and educational attainment. It is a term that describes any condition that reduces the hearing sensitivity of an individual and makes it difficult for that person to sense and interpret auditory signal. Babudoh (2021) explained that there are two kinds of hearing impairment based on the time of onset; congenital (pre-lingual) and adventitious (post-lingual) hearing impairment. Congenital hearing impairment is a condition where an individual was either born with a hearing impairment or he/she became hearing impaired before meaningful language was acquired, while post-lingual hearing impairment refers to a condition where an individual became hearing impaired after language acquisition. Students with post-lingual hearing impairment have the advantage of having acquired the language of the society to some extent, before the onset of the impairment.

The most devastating effects of hearing loss are that the normal development of speech and language is often disrupted. Such disruptions for example, ability to generate and comprehend language, grammar and social used (interaction) and limited vocabulary affect both genders; females and males alike. Such delays beyond certain points may warrant professional screening. Studies conducted by Dostal and Wolbers (2014), Karasu (2014) on oral language skills revealed that children with poor oral language tend to be poor readers as well. Inadequate oral language skills can contribute to reading difficulties in the area of concept formation and semantic knowledge. Oral language is often related with vocabulary as the major part, however, in the broadest sense, oral language is made up of phonology, grammar, morphology, vocabulary, discourse, and pragmatics. The attainment of these skills mostly begins at an early age, before pupils begin concentrating on print-based concepts such as sound-symbol resemblance and decoding. Because these skills are often developed early in life, children with limited oral language ability at the time they enter kindergarten are usually at a distinct disadvantage (Tallal, 2013).

Consequently, most individuals with a post-lingual hearing impairment must be taught pronunciation skills that normal-hearing children acquire during the first few years of life. To conserve the speech of individuals with post-lingual hearing impairment from further degeneration, researchers such as McLeod, and Baker, (2014) carried out a number of interventions and approaches to address articulation disorders- omission of sounds. A student with post-lingual hearing loss may find it difficult to regulate and monitor the speech through the ear due to the lack of auditory feedback. Such a student must be taught how to pronounce words correctly if not even the words acquired before the onset of the hearing impairment might fade away because of irregular or lack of usage.

Articulation disorder of omission; where a sound is omitted in a word. The omission of sounds can make speech very unintelligible, thereby resulting in a communication breakdown between the speaker and the listener. All communication disorders, error of omission of sound vary in degree. The severity ranges from mild or moderate (speech can be understood) to severe type when many sounds are pronounced poorly, the speech becomes unintelligible. It takes more than just one error to diagnose an individual as having such omission of sounds. Although no standard criteria for determining what constitute a disorder but several variables are to be considered by speech-language pathologist in arriving at such conclusions. For example, an individual must consistently mispronounce words which largely affect intelligibility and meaning of words, the attention of listeners is always drawn to the speaker and not the message. Speech and language pathologists with other multidisciplinary team will assess such individual's speech.

Several tests of articulation and speech are conducted, such as Denver articulation screening examination, Arizona articulation proficiency scale, assessment of sound awareness and production (Tye-Murray & Kirk, 2013; Satasha & Scott, 2017; Jill, 2017). These tests are to guide the professionals; speech-language pathologists to draw conclusions on the kinds of speech errors (substitution, omission, addition or distortion) an individual has, the nature of speech errors (moderate or severe), as well as the type of intervention that can be administered. Omission of words - leaving some specific letters/sounds out of the word-order, an example of speech omission saying...“at” for hat, “run” for running, “oo” for shoe, “play” for plays, “ake” for take, examples of omission of sound at the end are: “foing “ for following, “hungi” for hungry, “cu” instead of “cup,” “far” instead of “farm,” “compla” instead of “complain”. The consonants appear to be most frequently dropped at the ending of words (word-endings omission). However, this might be at the beginning or middle and sometimes at all three positions. When it occurs at the end of a word is called omission of word-endings. Dostal and Wolbers (2014) stated that the most noticeable characteristic of students with hearing impairment in writing at any given passage is the frequent omission of sounds. He argues that omission of words, as well as many other errors evident in the written/spoken language result from the failure to adopt a “discourse orientation”. He said, writing is often viewed as a laborious, sentence-by-sentence task, rather than an attempt at verbal expression. And the singular reason for this is the failure to use discourse structure in the writing and the lack of keeping rules of conversation normally acquired from monitoring ongoing verbal interaction

Possible causes of articulation disorders; omission of word-endings are hearing impairment, physical handicaps such as cerebral palsy, physical deformities such as cleft lips and palates, velopharyngeal dysfunction and resonance disorders all have one thing in common, airflow disruption (Kummer, 2016). Common airflow contributes to normal word pronunciation and speech and without this the individual will experience side effects which include weak or omitted consonants, short utterance length, nasal grimace and compensatory articulation productions. Other causes are genetic influences, apraxia and development disabilities; neurological malfunction (Bishop & Adams, 2013), (McLeod & Baker, 2016). The difficulty in expression by students with post-lingual hearing impairment affects general performances in oral English Language. Consequently, poor performance in Oral English and related courses in external examinations are evident.

Flash cards were used to serve as a therapy exercise that focused on building intimacy with certain words or sounds and physical exercises that focused on beef up the muscles that generate speech sounds. The researchers used target selection; target selection involved students practicing specific sounds or words to acquaint themselves with particular speech patterns. This includes difficult words or sounds that trigger speech disruption. Finally contextual utilization was also used, for the students to recognize speech sounds in different syllable-based contexts. All of the above were conducted to improve muscle strength, motor control and breathe control of the students. These activities helped developed fluency which created smoother speech that sounds closer to natural.

The study adopted the theory of Language Acquisition developed and propounded by B.F. Skinner in 1952. The theory states that language which is acquired through the process of learning and already acquired grammar is shaped into a correct form through reinforcement of other stimuli. This is applicable to students with post-lingual hearing impairment who have omission of words- ending. The principle is based on observation and imitation since already acquired grammar can be shaped into correct form through constant practice and rehearsal by use of flash cards.

Purpose of the study

The aim of this study was to assess the effects of flash cards drilling on omission of word-endings of students with post-lingual hearing impairment in Special Education Centre Bauchi. The specific objectives were to:

1. Find out the pretest mean on omission of word-ending of students with post-lingual hearing impairment after exposure to flash cards drill.
2. Examine whether or not flash cards drill reduce omission of word-endings of students with post-lingual hearing impairment based on gender.

Research Questions

1. To what extent can flash cards drill reduce the omission of word-ending of students with post-lingual hearing impairment after intervention?
2. To what extent can flash cards drill reduce the omission of word-endings of students with post-lingual hearing impairment after intervention based on gender?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference in the omission of word-endings mean scores of students with post-lingual hearing impairment after the intervention.
2. There is no significant difference in the omission of word-endings mean scores of students with post-lingual hearing impairment after the intervention based on gender.

Methodology

Research Design

Research adopted single-subject experimental research design; A-B-A-B variation of the reversal was used. This research design is useful when research is to determine whether an instructional material (intervention) is effective in meeting the needs of an individual or small group of individuals who wish to document it. The single-subject research helps to establish the effects of an intervention on a single individual. This informs the use to single-subject designs uses control procedures rather than control groups.

Study Area

The study was administered in Special Education Centre Yelwa Bauchi. The populations of the study consist of 15 students with post-lingual hearing impairment in Special Education Centre Yelwa, Bauchi.

Sampling Technique

The Sample consisted of 5 students in senior secondary school in Special Education centre Yelwa

Bauchi, with post lingual hearing impairment. While sample technique employed was purposive. The on-set of interest of the researchers was post-lingual, degree of loss was 66-85dB and age was 21-25 years in senior secondary school.

Instruments for data collection

The instruments for data collection were audiometer and word- recognition test. The audiological assessment and word-recognition tests were used to determine the baseline. Word- recognition was selected from Dolch 220 common words for both pre and post stages were made in form of flash cards.

Procedure for data collection

Twenty (20) words were selected from the Dolch 220 common words written on flash cards. Each week, five words were targeted and proper pronunciation was done by the researchers. The participants were encouraged to observe mouth shape of the researchers and imitate same. Researchers used adaptive transcription throughout the sessions of therapy. Drilling (therapy) sessions took two hours daily with an interval of 30 minutes short break for 6 weeks.

Statistical analysis

The research adopted both descriptive and inferential statistics in analysing the data for the study. Mean (X) and simple percentages (%) were utilized to answer the research questions, while t- test for dependent a sample was employed to test the two hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance and the second responses after 6 weeks of intervention.

Results

Table 1. Result of Students' Performance on Omission of Word Ending Before and After Intervention on Flash Cards

Students	Pretest	Post-test	Improvement	Percentage Improvement (%)
Student A	85	15	70	82
Student B	70	30	40	57
Student C	65	30	35	54
Student D	55	25	30	55
Student E	75	25	50	67
Mean(X)	70	25	45	64

Table 1 reveals the extent to which flash cards drillings reduced omission of word-endings among students with post-lingual hearing impairment after intervention. The analysis shows that the percentage pretest mean number was 70 and the post-test mean number was 25, with 45 (64%) reduction of errors among the students. This implies that the flash cards drillings reduced the numbers of errors on omission of word endings of students with post-lingual hearing impairment by 64%.

Table 2. Result of Students' Performance on Omission of Word Ending Before and After Intervention on Flash Cards based on Gender

Students	Gender	Pretest	Post-test	Improvement	Percentage Improvement (%)
Student A	Female	85	15	70	82
Student B	Male	70	30	40	57
Student C	Male	65	30	35	54
Student D	Male	55	25	30	55
Student E	Female	75	25	50	67
Mean (X)		70	25	45	64

Table 2 reveals the extent to which flash cards drillings reduced omission of word-endings among students with post-lingual hearing impairment after intervention based on gender. The analysis shows that the percentage pretest mean number was 70 and the post-test mean number was 25, with 45 (64%) reduction of errors among the students. The two females benefited the most, Student A being a female made 82% improvement, student E (female) also had 67% improvement. Both females had significant improvement much more than their male counterpart. The male students had average improvement of 57%.

Table 3. Comparison of Pretest and Post-test Mean Scores on Omission of Word-Ending on Flash Cards

Test	N	(X)	SD	df	t	p-value
Pretest	5	70.00	11.18	4	6.364	0.003
Post-test	5	25.00	6.12			

Table 3 shows the comparison of pretest and post-test mean scores for omission of word- ending on flash cards before and after intervention. Before intervention, pretest mean scores was 70 with standard deviation of 11.18. After intervention, post-test mean scores was 25 with a standard deviation of 6.12. The t-calculated was 6.364 with a p-value of 0.003. Since the p-value was less than 0.05, it means that there was a significant difference in the mean scores hence the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative was accepted.

Table 4. Comparison of Pretest Mean Scores on Omission of Word-Ending on Flash Cards Based on Gender

Gender	N	(X)	SD	df	t	p-value
Males	3	73.33	10.41			
Females	2	65.00	14.14	4	0.78	0.56

Table 4 shows the comparison of pretest mean scores for omission of word- ending on flash cards intervention based on gender before intervention, pretest mean scores for the males was 73.33 with standard deviation of 10.41 while females mean scores was 65.00 with a standard deviation of 14.14. The t-value was 0.78 with a p-value of 0.56. Since the p-value was greater than 0.05, it means that there was no significant difference in the mean scores hence the null hypothesis was accepted.

Discussion

This study investigated the effects of flash cards drillings on omission of word-endings performance of students with post-lingual hearing impairment in Special Education Centre Bauchi. The aim was to assist the students to pronounce words correctly in order to reduce the number of errors in omission of word-endings made while communicating in the classroom or outside the classroom.

The data from this study were analysed and used to answer the research questions and also test hypotheses administered. The results of this study revealed that omission of word-endings performance of the students after intervention greatly improved as the students made fewer errors in the areas of omission assessed and treated.

Analysis on research question one revealed the extent to which flash cards drillings reduced the omission of word-endings among students with post-lingual hearing impairment in senior secondary school in Special Education Centre Bauchi. The study revealed that flash cards drillings reduced the number of errors on the omission of the word-ending of students with post-lingual hearing impairment drastically. Before the therapy, all the students omitted most of their word endings such as ing, s, ed, ren, ly. But after the intervention, the errors of omission of the word- ending were reduced. This confirms the position of Dodd, Crosbie, McIntosh, Harvey, Liddy, Fonteyn, Pinchin and Rigby (2008) that, the extent of progress made by children with phonological and articulation disorders was dependent on the nature of remediating exercise they were exposed to. The children made drastic progress after therapy in terms of pronunciation accuracy. This study is in line with study conducted by Aderibgibe, Idemudia and Iheke (2015) entitled 'effect of activity-based instructional strategy on learning outcomes of students with post-lingual severe hearing impairment'. The result showed that there was a significant difference between the activity-based strategy and the conventional method. The activity-based in this instance is flash cards drillings and adaptive transcriptions which assisted the students to remedy their pronunciation errors- omission of word- endings because they actively participated in all the activities from the beginning to the end of the therapy.

Recommendations

Based on the results the following recommendations were made:

1. Students with omission of word-endings should go through therapeutic sessions with all seriousness and determination. They can go beyond the stipulated period of therapy in order to sustain and conserve the residual language.
2. All schools with post-lingual hearing-impaired students should allot periods for aural

rehabilitation where a speech therapist would drill students with such needs. This should be in the school's time table; the intervention should start in JS one so that the acquired skill will help them all through their seniors' schools and subsequently university education.

Conclusion

From the investigation, interpretations and analyses of tables that were used to answer research questions and test the hypotheses formulated in this research. It was observed that flash cards drill was found to be useful, highly motivational and effective. This is because the students were drilled severally during the period of intervention. Exposure to flash cards drill therapy via adaptive transcription has also made students to improve on their self-confidence during interaction with their peers so much that they desire that the therapy should continue as long as it was convenient for the researchers. It can therefore be concluded that flash cards drill transformed the students' pronunciation and reduced omission of words-ending. This had impacted in the performances in oral related subjects.

References

- Aderibigbe, S. A., Idemudia, E. S., & Iheke, C. B. (2015). *Effect of activity-based instructional strategy on learning outcomes of students with hearing impairment*. In E. P. Ntukidem (Ed.), *Special needs education*. University of Calabar Press.
- Babudoh, G. B. (2021). *Rudiments of audiology*. Adage Communications.
- Bishop, Dorothy V. M., & Adams, Catherine A. (2013). Prospective study of the relationship between specific language impairment, phonological disorders and reading retardation. *Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry*, 31(7), 1027–1050.
- Dodd, Barbara, Crosbie, S., McIntosh, B., Holm, A., Harvey, C., Liddy, M., Fontyne, K., Pinchin, B., & Rigby, H. (2008). The impact of selecting different contrasts in phonological therapy. *International Journal of Speech-Language Pathology*, 10(5), 334–345. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14417040701732590>
- Dostal, Hannah, & Wolbers, Kimberly. (2014). Developing language and writing skills of deaf and hard of hearing students: A simultaneous approach. *Literacy Research and Instruction*, 53(3), 245–268.
- Jill, S. (2017). *Speech disorders: Causes and treatment*. Medical News Today. <https://www.medicalnewstoday.com/articles/324764>
- Karasu, H. P. (2014). Determination of hearing-impaired students' requirements for editing and revision of written texts. *Educational Sciences: Theory & Practice*, 14(3), 1089–1098.
- Kummer, A. (2016). Disorders of resonance and air flow secondary to cleft palate and/or velopharyngeal dysfunction. *Seminars in Speech and Language*, 32(2), 141–149.
- McLeod, S., & Baker, E. (2016). *Children's speech: An evidence-based approach*. Pearson. Pressley, M. (2015). *Dolch professional development guide*. SRA.
- McLeod, Sharynne, & Baker, Elise. (2014). Speech-language pathologists' practices regarding assessment, analysis, target selection, intervention, and service delivery for children with speech sound disorders. *Clinical Linguistics & Phonetics*, 28, 508–531.
- Satasha, L. G., & Scott, C. M. (2016). *The history of speech and language impairments*. In F. R. Anthony, F. E. Obiakor, & J. P. Bakken (Eds.), *History of speech education* (pp. 7–12). Emerald Group Publishing.
- Tallal, Paula. (2013). *Experimental studies of language learning impairment: From research to remediation*. In D. V. M. Bishop & L. B. Leonard (Eds.), *Speech and language impairment in children: Causes, characteristics, intervention and outcome* (pp. 131–155). Psychology Press.
- Tye-Murray, Nancy, & Kirk, K. I. (2013). Vowel and diphthong production by young users of cochlear implants and the relationships between phonetic level evaluation and spontaneous speech. *Journal of Speech and Hearing Research*, 36(1), 488–502.